

Interconnectors Sub-Working Group
SEN Markets & Regulations Working Group
University of Bath
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Professor Derek Bunn
Chair, Panel of Technical Experts (PTE)
Department for Business, Energy, and Industrial Strategy

Dear Professor Bunn,

We wish to provide feedback on the summary briefing note from National Grid ESO, ‘Modelling de-rating factors for interconnected countries in the 2021 Electricity Capacity Report’. We welcome the request to provide feedback on this methodology. Interconnection to other markets clearly has the potential to increase the resilience and economic efficiency of the GB energy system, and so the Interconnectors Subgroup of the Supergen Energy Network (SEN) Markets & Regulations Working Group were very interested to read about the developments on the methodology that have been considered in the past year. In general, it is our view that the sensitivities considered in Table 1 of the briefing note are clearly justified.

There are two distinct points we would like to raise to the PTE on the modelling of the de-rating factors for interconnected countries more generally. The topics are in terms of the consideration of a weather and climate change data strategy for the Northwest European region, and the effects of interconnector exports on de-rating margins during stress periods in interconnected countries.

Weather Data Sources and Climate Change

The first point we wish to raise is on the topic of the inclusion of more weather data, and particularly how climate change could impact on supply and demand calculations both in GB and in interconnected countries. The weather dataset that NGENSO uses should include climate variability, capture extremes, and account for climate change. The first two of these points can be achieved (to a reasonable extent) by including several decades of weather data, as NGENSO are doing. However, our understanding is that the effects of climate change are not yet accounted for. It our view that NGENSO ought to have a clear strategy for determining how climate-change corrections can be incorporated into their analysis, where there are known to be clear impacts on supply and demand.

Figure 1: Population-weighted temperatures have grown at a rate of 0.035°C per year in France, with GCM models projecting increases in temperature of up to 1.12°C over 20 years. Quantiles are calculated based on the hourly temperature distribution of each winter from ERA5. GCM 1–3 correspond to EC-EARTH3P, EC-EARTH3P-HR and MOHC-HH-3hr models [2], whilst the ERA5 reanalysis is used as the ground truth.

For example, over the past 40 years there have been marked increases in temperature across Northwest Europe, with population-weighted winter temperatures of the past 40 years for GB and France estimated to increase at an average rate of 0.034°C per year and $0.035^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{yr}$, respectively (temperatures in France for winters from 1979 to 2019 are plotted in Figure 1). Analysis of the outputs of three General Circulation Models (GCMs)¹ indicate that mean temperatures between 2000 and 2035 could increase at a similar rate; this is also comparable to the reported 0.9°C increase in average UK temperatures seen by comparing the period 1961-1990 against 2009-2018 in [1].

The ‘Change Factor’ method (or ‘Delta Method’) [3] can be used to correct for this climate change signal, mapping the weather from historic years to the current 2021 climate using a linear correction factor. Again, using the example of the French and GB systems, the mean temperature of the climate from 1980 to 2020 could then increase by 0.86°C in GB and 1.12°C in France. Because temperatures before 1990 were often the coldest winters, this de-trending can have quite significant impacts on temperature distributions. For example, taking this effect into account leads to an almost halving in the probability of the population-weighted temperature of France dropping below freezing—12.2% of days are below this threshold in the historic

¹Post-processing of the outputs of these GCMs and Figures 1 and 2 have been created as part of the CLEARHEADS project, led by the University of Reading.

Figure 2: Weekday peak demand for 16/17-18/19 winters against population-weighted temperature.

dataset, compared to just 6.5% once the temperatures are corrected with the Change Factor method.

The impact of this temperature correction on capacity adequacy will vary across interconnected countries: we estimate the weekday peak demand-temperature sensitivity for the twenty weeks from the start of November (discounting Christmas) to be 580 MW/°C for GB and 2047 MW/°C for France, as shown in Figure 2. We have calculated this to lead to a reduction in the three-per-year peak demands of 550 MW and 2230 MW for GB and French systems, respectively. At a net cost of new entry of £49/kW/yr, a reduction in capacity requirements at this level leads to cost savings of £27m per year in the GB system; on the other hand, the French system could also show significantly inflated demand during periods of system stress. Some of these ideas are explored in the wider European setting in [4].

It is worth noting that temperature extremes as cold as those seen in the 1980s are still possible, with the severe Texas blackouts this winter [5] highlighting the clear need for capacity planning that is robust to adverse meteorological conditions. However, the stress-testing against extremes requires different techniques to the long-term, ‘typical’ climate modelling considered in the central scenarios as described above. Further work could consider how to combine historic weather data with appropriate energy data to define severe (but credible) meteorological scenarios that would complement the supply- and demand-based scenarios listed in Table 1 of the briefing note. Such extreme events would therefore need to be updated regularly as demand and renewable penetrations across Europe evolve [6, 7]. Such analysis could also include, for example, exploring the weather record before 1980, with centennial-scale reanalyses such as ERA20C [8] capturing the evolution

of weather over much longer periods than those presently considered.

Impacts of Shortfalls in Interconnected Countries

The second point we wish to raise with regards to the overall philosophy of the approach is with regards to the conditions at which the de-rating factors are calculated. The briefing note states that, in the context of developing the GB base case, stress periods are only counted if there is ‘loss of load after interconnector imports have been considered’. In the determination of these imports, it is stated, ‘factors like market pricing are not relevant’, and that it is assumed that ‘all the capacity [in interconnected countries] is available to provide imports to Great Britain’.

Based on the points described above, we understand that the *only* way in which an interconnected country can have a de-rating factor lower than 100% is if that country is also at the point at which it would also have a shortfall. In other words, it is implicit that interconnected countries are willing to continue fully exporting right up to the point they have zero margin, and only then will exports to GB begin to decrease.

This lack of reciprocity appears to be problematic, particularly given that interconnected countries are modelled with a loss of load probability similar to that of the GB system (e.g., it is presumed that the same 3 hour LOLE standards might be used for other continental European countries). At other time periods, these systems would therefore be acting to diminish the GB system security with exports from GB (noting that weather and temporal factors affect the margin on both the supply and demand side), but in the current formulation these possibilities cannot affect the de-rating factors. Marginal reductions in system security with increased interconnection have been demonstrated as a possibility for GB interconnection with Ireland in, for example, [9]. In addition, through-flows (e.g., GB importing from France and exporting to Ireland) and interconnector loop flows (GB importing from France and exporting to Belgium to avoid congestion) also add complexity.

It is therefore our view that the assumed TSO policies that are assumed to operate under [10] should be built into the analysis in a more transparent way, particularly with respect to shortfalls occurring in systems other than GB.

Closing remarks

We recognise that there is limited time before the Electricity Capacity Report is published, and so it likely to be impractical for further detailed analysis to be undertaken this year. Nevertheless we hope these points will be of interest to the PTE in their consideration of NGESO's approach in future.

If either of these issues are ambiguous or further information is required then do not hesitate to get in touch.

Yours sincerely,

SEN Interconnectors Markets & Regulations Subworking Group

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